

Assessing Training Effectiveness at Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi

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Abstract

Training is HR activity which helps to develop the skill of an employee in a regular mode. Since the organization say, Karpagaa Calendar, Sivakasi faces many problems regarding enhancing the productivity of the employees the study entitled “Training Manual for workers of Karpagaa Calendars”, has planned to faces an innovative strategy to improve the same, in a continuous manner. Effective training and development programs aimed at improving the employees’ performance. Training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance. Training could be given through different methods such as on the coaching and cooperation and participation by the subordinates. This team work enable employees to actively participate on the job and produces better performance, hence improving organizational performance. The study is intended to evaluate employee training in the organization. A good employee training principle or procedure is essential to achieve the genuine intention of promotion of employee training should not be considered as a matter of charity. Training must be adored by the employees and should satisfy their need. The basis of training must be broad so that large number of employees should be covered by them. This has been planned to achieve in their research.

Training is important and an imperative tool for the organization to revamp the performance of all the personnel for organizational growth and success. It is beneficial to both employers and employees of an organization. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is trained well.

Statement of the Problem

This study is an attempt to examine the effectiveness of training practices practiced in Sri Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi. This study has made to find out the new training practices to be adopted by the employer of Karpagaa Calendars.

Objectives

1. To study the different methods of training programmes performed in Karpagaa Calendars.
2. To study the effectiveness of training programme by collecting the data from the employees.

3. To know the satisfaction level of employees towards training programme and suggest measures to improved it.

Scope of the Study

The study of training effectiveness of workers was carried out at Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi for a period of 4 Months. This study has paved way for orienting new employees to the environment and there by training them for both job and career advancements with the advent of designing and developing a Training Manual.

Limitations of the Study

- The research findings are restricted to employees of Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi.
- The period of the study is confined to four months i.e., from December 2017 to March 2018.

Research Design

- The research design specifies the procedure for conducting and controlling the research project. The choice of particular research design would follow from the problem.
- The current study is based on Descriptive Research. This type of research aims at highlighting the state of affairs of existing problems. It is a report of happenings both past and present.

Sources of Data

1. Primary Data

Data collected through interview schedule from the employees of Karpagaa Calendars.

2. Secondary Data

Data collected through journals from websites.

Data Collection Instrument

A well-defined interview schedule is used effectively to gather information on both the overall performance of the test system as well as information on specific components of the systems. It was carefully prepared and specially numbered. The objective attain to the employee benefits. The questions were arranged in proper order, in accordance with the relevance.

Population

There are 130 workers working in Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi.

Sampling Size

Sample size of 50 respondents was interviewed for the research.

Sampling Unit

Employees of Karpagaa Calendars, Sivakasi were considered as the sampling unit of the study.

Period of the study

The period of the study is restricted for a period of four months i.e., from December 2017 to March 2018.

Sampling Technique

It this method the sample units are chosen primarily on the basis of the convenience of the investigator. Convenience sampling refers to selecting a sample of study objective based on

convenience. Thus a research study may include study objects which are conveniently located, willing to co-operate in offering the necessary data and in the process one would derive the advantage of economy in cost or time. It helps to understand the possible variability or response within a short span of time and cost.

Sampling Tools

Simple statistical tools such as percentages and bar diagram were used for data analysis.

Findings

- Most of 44% of the respondents are between the age group of 20 to 25 years.
- Most of 44% of the respondents are work in less than 3 years.
- Majority of 66% of the respondents are work in first organization.
- Majority of 52% of the respondent are highly satisfied the expected at the work.
- Most of 44% of the respondent are satisfied the everyday work.
- Most of 42% of the respondent are satisfied their appropriate task variety.
- Majority of 54% of the respondent are satisfied a job that matches our skills.
- Most of 36% of the respondents have highly satisfied to perform our job in the organization.
- Majority of 52% of respondents have satisfied the organization culture.
- Majority of 52% of respondents have satisfied the organization rewards.
- Most of 40% of respondents have satisfied the comfortable working in the organization.
- Most of 34% of respondents have satisfied the organization production area.
- Most of 46% of respondents have satisfied a work in safe environment.
- Most of 36% of respondents have satisfied our work with our personal relationship.
- Most of 46% of respondents have satisfied our salary.
- Most of 44% of respondents have satisfied our employee benefits.
- Most of 44% of respondents have satisfied immediate rewards for the employee in the organization.
- Most of 48% of respondents have satisfied the performance goals of the organization.
- Most of 48% of respondents have satisfied the performance is regularly tracked and measured.
- Majority of 52% of respondents have Satisfied our performance on both the employee and supervisor.
- Most of 44% of the respondents have highly satisfied our performance is appropriately rewarded in the form incentives.
- Most of 46% of respondents have satisfied our performance measures is used as criteria for promotion.
- Most of 36% of respondents have satisfied to supportive and productive team.
- Most of 46% of the respondents have highly satisfied to variety of training programs are offered to improve skills.
- Most of 46% of respondents have satisfied to feel attached with our company team.
- Most of 44% of respondents have satisfied the opportunity to grow with the organization.
- Majority of 56% of respondents have Satisfied the work in a trusting and ethical environment.

Suggestions

- Awareness about Training manual can be given to the employees, so that they can be trained throughout their employment.
- Training manual can be depicted in a flowchart form and can be displayed in each and every Department, so that it motivates the employees to reach their career advancements.

- Training manual can be used as a standard in case of Performance Appraisal, so that the pre training needs can be assessed well in advance.
- Employees shall be strictly informed to adhere to the training manual, thus the overall objective of the organization can be achieved.
- Proper benchmarking strategies can be undertaken to upgrade the training manual regularly, which will assist the employees to involve in their work activity and thereby make them empowered.

Conclusion

The researcher has taken a step ahead by designing a model called Training Manual for employees, as an outcome to the problem of measuring the impact of training. By the way of this model the researcher has stressed emphasis of two core areas (Remedial and Promotional Training) of employee performance. Once the shortfall in any of the specified area is highlighted efforts in that area can be extended by the organizations. It tends to provide value to companies expenditure. It also creates a sense of belonging among employees. This initiative is getting accepted by the HR's of the concerned organizations. This outcome can also be shared with all manufacturing concerns irrespective of their size to resolve their basic issues of Employee Training. The contribution of this research is that it has touched almost all aspects of training and has suggested the ways to make it more uniform and more knowledgeable so as to bring new reforms in this field and help the knowledge corpus grow.

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